

BARRIERS TO FINANCIAL INCLUSION FOR MUSLIM WOMEN: A CASE STUDY FROM INDIA

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Abstract

Despite the government's financial inclusion drive, women in India remain diffident participants in banking. Particularly so, women who are illiterate, finds the study of an adult literacy programme for women in rural north India. The study also discovers that among its women research subjects, Muslims are the weakest at accessing and availing banking services. This is plausible given that Muslim women have the lowest literacy rates in India as per the last count in census 2011. Beyond establishing this correlation, however, deeper investigations reveal that illiteracy is only one among the many impediments between Muslim women and banks. In fact, a complex amalgam of religious-socio-economic barriers, including illiteracy, keeps them from banking. This article draws from the study to construct a narrative around detection of these barriers. And sources insights from the responses of Muslim women and their community as they respond to the study's findings and offer solutions to overcome these barriers..

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Introduction

The distance between women and banks in India seems to resist efforts at reduction. Aggressive drives have seen accounts being opened for millions of women since the launch of our national mission for financial inclusion, the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), in 2014 (Department of Financial Services, Ministry of Finance, GOI, 2021). Actually, as per the last publicly available records in December 2021, women now hold nearly 56 per cent of the 441 million Jan Dhan accounts. Yet, whether women make for active account holders remains a persisting concern. Providing recent reason for such worry, a survey published by Indus Action finds that 40 per cent of women Jan Dhan account holders could not access the monthly INR 500 Covid-19 relief that the government had transferred into their accounts between April and June 2020 (Patel et al., 2020).

Research and reportage document several factors as keeping women away from meaningful engagement with banks and banking. Account dormancy because of infrequent or no usage and long-distances to banks in remote rural areas figure commonly among such issues (Financial Inclusion Insights Survey, 2018). For this article, however, an especially relevant reason for the distance between women and banks is that gender is not the only individual characteristic that appears to matter for the likelihood of owning an account. Poor education levels aggravate existing deprivations in account ownership faced by adults in general, and women in particular. As per The Global Findex Database 2017, account ownership is lower among less educated adults, and it decreases with lower levels of education (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). This burdens financial inclusion campaigns in India with yet another colossal problem, given that our total illiteracy rate stands at 27.1 per cent, with female illiteracy at an even higher at 35.4 per cent (Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, Ministry of Home Affairs, 2011).

Disturbingly, despite a series of educational programmes and reforms in India, communities that are variously vulnerable and marginalised due to the issues they face in integrating with mainstream society continue to remain backward on the literacy front. With a literacy rate of 69 per cent, Muslims are the least educated among all the religious communities in India. And Muslim women have an even lower literacy rate at 62 per cent.

The worryingly high levels of illiteracy appear to be playing out in Muslim women's inability and ineptitude with banking as evidenced in the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16. The NFHS-4 survey shows that Muslim women's access to money and awareness, and use of microcredit, is poorer than for Indian women in total ((International Institute for Population Sciences & Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2017). The relevant details from the NFHS-4 survey are listed in Table 1 below.

Table I: Women's access to money and credit

		Total (%)	Muslim (%)
Women's access to money	Percentage who have money that they can decide how to use	41.7	39.3
	Percentage who have bank or savings account that they themselves use	53	44.5
Women's knowledge and use of microcredit programmes	Percentage who have known of a microcredit programme	40.8	35.4
	Percentage who have taken a loan from a microcredit programme	7.7	5.6

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

In this article, we present the study of a women's literacy programme that provides empirical evidence of the relationship between Muslim women, their illiteracy and their exclusion from the banking system. And delves further to discover barriers beyond illiteracy that add to the disconnect between Muslim women and banks. The study was conducted in early 2021.

Study intervention and site: An initiative by Development Alternatives (DA), the study-programme TARA Akshar+ (TA+) is an ICT-based programme to make women functionally literate.² The programme consists of two components: computer-enabled lessons in Hindi and basic mathematics over 56 days, topped by literacy retention sessions over six months. TA+ has benefited 23000 women across 90 villages in the Aurai block in eastern Uttar Pradesh's (UP) Bhadohi district, the Lalitpur block in UP's Lalitpur district and the Bhagwanpur block in Uttarakhand's Hardwar district in its third phase since 2017.³

Research design: The study comprises two parts, each of which derive a descriptive-label from the findings that emerge from it: i) Discovering barriers; ii) Understanding barriers.

The first part, 'Discovering barriers', follows a sequential explanatory mixed methods research design to evaluate the combined outcomes of both components of the programme. Informed by Creswell (2013), this design is characterised by the collection and analysis of quantitative data in the first

2 ICT is the short form for Information and Communication Technology. Use of ICT in education supports, enhances and optimises the delivery of information. It can lead to improved student learning and better teaching methods.

3 The first phase of TARA Akshar+ (TA+), also known as the pilot phase started in 2013 across three locations in Uttar Pradesh. The second phase that started in 2014 extended the programme to nine locations. The programme has benefited two lakh women overall in all the three phases combined.

phase, followed by qualitative data collection in the second phase (Creswell, 2013). The qualitative data collection in fact builds on the results of the quantitative round. Finally, both types of data are integrated to make for the study's analysis and findings.

The integrated findings are then shared with stakeholders to solicit in-community interpretation and analysis in the second part of the study, 'Understanding barriers'. This is done in keeping with the principles of participatory research, which aims to ensure that studies are not monolithic bodies of ideas and methods but rather a pluralistic orientation to knowledge making and social change (Chambers, 2008). Stakeholder interpretation of findings is therefore sought in keeping with the belief that a variety of perspectives, especially from within the community, will enrich the study's inferences. Qualitative research methods are employed to collect data.

The synthesis of findings from both parts of the study makes for the study's conclusion. The research design is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Sampling:

Quantitative: The survey respondents for the study comprise women participants of the programme or the 'treatment group'. And women from similar villages who have not participated in the programme or the 'control group'. A two-stage cluster sampling method is used to select neo-literate women programme participants. Since the adult literacy programme was implemented in 90 villages in three districts, villages are considered clusters and stratified across the districts. This ensures representation of all three districts. The villages are ranked on their initial female literacy situation (as per the 2011 census) and divided into tertiles. Three villages are chosen from each tertile, creating a pool of 27 treatment villages to be surveyed. In the second stage, after selecting the villages, neo-literates (programme participants) to be surveyed are sampled. Then, 25 women are randomly selected from each selected village. To sample for the control group of illiterate women, a cohort of villages is created in the same districts. Then,

using the propensity score matching (PSM) technique, the closest matches to programme villages are identified.⁴ Villages are matched on demographic and economic characteristics, also access. One control village is identified against every treatment village. Thus, a total of 27 control villages are identified.⁵ Then, households are randomly selected, and literacy and numeracy tests are administered to identify the illiterate women to be surveyed.

Qualitative: For the qualitative research in the first part of the study ('Discovering barriers'), subjects are selected from one surveyed village in each of three programme blocks.⁶ First, ten neo-literate programme participants are chosen in each of the three selected villages to partake in focus group discussions (FGDs).⁷ The selection of villages and discussants is guided by the purposive sampling technique that is primarily used in qualitative studies. This technique is defined as selecting units (e.g., individuals, groups of individuals and institutions) based on specific purposes associated with answering a research study's questions (Teddlie & Yu, 2007). In keeping with which, discussants are chosen using programme data and information to ensure that they are representative of typical programme participants characterised by demographics such as age, education and marital status. Also, key-informants (KIs) for in-depth interviews (IDIs) are 'deliberately selected for the important information they are able to provide' so as to aid the study's comprehension of the programme's immediate settings, its processes and progress.⁸

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- 4 Propensity Score Matching (PSM) is an econometric technique to match treated and untreated subjects who share a similar value/score.
 - 5 On the field, however, the study was forced to drop 12 villages as a response to the exigencies of Covid-19. The sample size of women in the control group was also affected due to the same constraints.
 - 6 The survey in Uttar Pradesh's Bhadohi district has been conducted in 10 and 20 villages in its Bhadohi and Aurai blocks respectively. For the sake of brevity this article refers them together as Aurai. Hence from now on, we refer to three study blocks in our article instead of three study districts.
 - 7 FGD or focus group discussion is a qualitative research method and data collection technique in which a selected group of people discusses a given topic or issue in-depth, facilitated by a professional, external moderator. This method serves to solicit participants' attitudes and perceptions, knowledge and experiences, and practices, shared in the course of interaction. https://www.herd.org.np/uploads/frontend/Publications/PublicationsAttachments/1485497050-Focus%20Group%20Discussion_0.pdf; https://www.swisstph.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/SwissTPH/Topics/Society_and_Health/Focus_Group_Discussion_Manual_van_Eeuwijk_Anghehrn_Swiss_TPH_2017.pdf
 - 8 IDIs or in-depth-interviews are a qualitative data collection method that allows for the collection of a large amount of information about the behaviour, attitude and perception of the interviewees. It involves conducting intensive individual interviews to explore interviewee perspectives on a particular idea, programme or situation. Interviews are often used to provide context to other data (such as outcome data), offering a more complete picture of what happened in the programme and why. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/in-depth-interviews/>; https://donate.pathfinder.org/site/DocServer/m_e_tool_series_indepth_interviews.pdf

Sampling for the second part of the study ('Understanding barriers') is dictated by the findings from the first part. Neo-literate women programme participants and KIs who are best equipped to interpret and analyse the first-parts' findings are selected for IDIs. Again, the selection of these interviewees is guided by the purposive sampling technique to serve the study's research objective. The study sites, tools, subjects and sample sizes are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Study sites, tools, subjects and sample sizes

	STUDY (Discovering barriers)		INTERPRETING STUDY (Understanding barriers)
Research type	QUANTITATIVE	QUALITATIVE	QUALITATIVE
	• Aurai: 14 villages (9T+5C)	• Aurai: 1 village	• Bhagwanpur: 1 village
Sites	• Lalitpur: 14 villages (9T+5C)	• Lalitpur: 1 village	
	• Bhagwanpur: 14 villages (9T+5C)	• Bhagwanpur: 1 village	
Tools	• Literacy-numeracy tests	• Focus group discussions (FGDs)	• In-depth interviews
	• Survey	• In-depth interviews (IDIs)	
	• Neo-literate participants (T) programme	• Neo-literate programme participants	• Neo-literate Muslim programme participants
Subjects	• Illiterate women in matched villages (C)	• Key informants: TARA Sahelis (local women recruits for programme's literacy retention component); literacy instructor; programme field staff; sarpanchs; school teachers; graduate women village residents; family members	• Key informants: Literacy instructor (local Muslim woman); Deputy Sarpanch; principal of local private middle school (graduate Muslim woman); member from local NGO (financial literacy trainer associated with the programme in Uttar Pradesh)

Table 2: Continued

Research type	STUDY (Discovering barriers)		INTERPRETING STUDY (Understanding barriers)
	QUANTITATIVE	QUALITATIVE	QUALITATIVE
		of neo-literate programme participants; members from local NGOs (TA+ partners, non-partners)	
Sample size	• Treatment : 623	• Neo-literate programme participants: 30	• Neo-literate Muslim programme participants: 1
	• Control: 308	• Key informants: 33	• Key informants: 4

T: Treatment | C: Control

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

FINDINGS

A. Discovering barriers

1. Women's illiteracy is an obstruction to financial inclusion⁹

Our survey confirms that the government's aggressive financial inclusion drive (including, and especially, through the Jan Dhan Yojana) has made banks accessible to near-equal large numbers of women in both the treatment and control villages. However, the drive seems to have fallen short of engaging women actively in banking. The study discovers that women's illiteracy is a critical barrier to their meaningful financial inclusion.

The study finds an inextricable link between literacy, the capacity to negotiate banks, and a newfound sense of empowerment in neo-literate women (who have participated in the adult literacy programme). A sizeable 61 per cent of the neo-literates report transacting their bank accounts by themselves in the last six months. The corresponding figure for this among the illiterate women in the control group is only 33 per cent. Also, the scores on financial literacy are markedly higher for neo-literate women. The results are listed in Table 3.

⁹ The findings sub-headed 'Women's illiteracy is an obstruction to financial inclusion', draws from this article's companion publication: Wadhwa, S. 2020. Women's financial inclusion is critical in Covid-19 times, but illiteracy is a barrier. *Gender & Inclusion*. Centre for Development Policy and Practice. <https://www.cdpp.co.in/gender-and-inclusion>

Table 3: Survey results on banking awareness, activity and financial literacy

QUESTIONS	RESPONSE	RESULT (Lalitpur, Aurai, Bhagwanpur)	
		Treatment	Control
Do you have a bank account?	Yes	88.91	85.81
If yes, whose name is the account in?	Own name	97.5	92.23
Do you know the name of your bank?	Could answer	82.41	38.71
Have you transacted your account on your own in the last 6 months?	Yes	61.01	33.23
Imagine that five brothers have INR 1000 in total. If they have to share the money equally how much does each one get?	INR 200	90.33	41.61
You lent INR 100 to a friend and she gives you INR 102 back next month. How much interest has she paid on the loan?	2 per cent	65.45	6.45

Note: All figures are in percentages

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

The study's qualitative research validates the survey findings mentioned above. In FGDs conducted with them, neo-literate women say that literacy has equipped them with skills and confidence to work their way in banks independently. They can now sign and fill forms, withdraw money. A few go as far as to say that they can even read passbooks. Their family and community members further substantiate this causal link between women's literacy and a rise in their self-esteem and capacity to negotiate the outside world, including banks. The ability to read, write and count, observes the sarpanch of one of the study villages has enabled women to be more than just passive participants in household financial decisions, SHG meetings (self-help group) and as bank account holders.¹⁰ Neo-literate women who do not have bank accounts yet express earnest intent to open personal accounts. Literacy has certainly caused a surge in banking activities among women, confirms the branch manager at a national bank in a study village. Adding that this exposure to banks opens up a new world of financial possibilities for women.

¹⁰ A Self Help Group (SHG) is a community-based group with 10 to 25 members. SHG members are usually women from similar social and economic backgrounds, voluntarily coming together to save small sums of money, on a regular basis. In India, RBI (Reserve Bank of India) regulations mandate that banks offer financial services, including collateral free loans to these groups, on very low interest rates. This allows poor women to circumvent the challenges of exclusion from institutional financial services. SHGs are widely used by microfinance institutions.

2. Muslim women face barriers to financial inclusion, other than illiteracy

Next, a sole focus on the scores of the neo-literate programme participants reveals that the Muslim among these women lag in accessing banks and banking services. This despite them topping the literacy test and standing second in the numeracy test.

To begin with, results of the literacy and numeracy tests administered along with the survey questionnaire show women participants in all the three programme blocks performing well.^{11,12} This in turn, establishes that programme implementation has been consistently efficient across the blocks. Having said which, participants in Bhagwanpur secure the top and second ranks by scoring marginally better in the language and mathematics tests respectively. Additionally, they outperform women in the other blocks in answering the survey's financial literacy questions, which are based on basic mathematics. It is, therefore, remarkable that the survey finds women in Bhagwanpur at the bottommost in access, awareness and use of banks.

Only 82 per cent of the neo-literate programme participants have bank accounts in Bhagwanpur, compared to a considerably higher 95 and 90 per cent in Lalitpur and Aurai respectively. In fact, not only do women in Bhagwanpur lag in account ownership, even those who are account holders seem passive compared to their counterparts in the two other blocks. While an overwhelming 82 per cent account-holding women in Lalitpur and 90 per cent in Aurai know the names of their banks, only 72 per cent of Bhagwanpur's account-holding women do. Also, a meagre 40 per cent women in Bhagwanpur say they have transacted their bank accounts on their own in the last six months. The corresponding percentages for Lalitpur and Aurai are substantially higher at 73 and 70 per cent respectively.

Next, an analysis of survey results from the control villages in all three blocks further confirms that factors other than illiteracy obstruct Bhagwanpur's women, both neo-literate and illiterate, from engaging with banks. Of illiterate women in the control villages in all three blocks, those in Bhagwanpur notch up the worst percentage for bank ownership. Also, of the illiterate women in Bhagwanpur's control village who own bank accounts, only 17 per cent have transacted their accounts, compared to 34 and 49 per cent of their counterparts in Lalitpur and Aurai respectively. These

11 The literacy and numeracy test follows an evaluation format designed by ASER. ASER Centre was established in 2005 as an autonomous assessment, survey, evaluation and research unit within the Pratham network. ASER has been publishing annual reports on rural Indian children's schooling status and basic learning levels. <http://www.asercentre.org/#hrz7e>

12 Location-wise results show 91.63, 85.02 and 65.1 per cent of neo-literate women programme participants are able to read a paragraph in Bhagwanpur, Lalitpur and Aurai respectively. And 66.18, 65.52 and 51.9 per cent of them are able to do summations in Lalitpur, Bhagwanpur and Aurai respectively.

percentages make evident that something is keeping all women in Bhagwanpur, both neo-literate and illiterate, from physically accessing and transacting in banks. The results are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Block-wise survey results on banking awareness, activity and financial literacy

QUESTIONS	Options	Combined		Lalitpur		Aurai		Bhagwanpur	
		T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C
Do you have a bank account?	Yes	88.91	85.81	95.17	94.59	89.05	88.8	81.77	73
If yes, whose name is the account in?	In your name	97.5	92.23	96.95	94.29	97.86	98.9	98.8	85
Do you know the name of your bank?	Yes	82.41	38.71	89.37	20.72	84.76	65.3	72.41	32
Have you transacted your account on your own in the last 6 months?	Yes	61.01	33.23	72.95	34.23	69.05	49	39.41	17
Imagine that five brothers have INR 1000 in total. If they have to share the money equally how much does each one get?	INR 200	90.33	41.61	95.65	26.13	83.81	59.2	92.12	41
You lent INR 100 to a friend and she gives you INR 102 back next month. How much interest has she paid on the loan?	2 per cent	65.45	6.45	68.12	0.9	50	17.4	78.82	2

T: Treatment | C: Control

Note: All figures are in percentages

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

The qualitative data drawn from FGDs conducted with the neo-literate programme participants in all three blocks further consolidate the quantitative findings tabled above. The data show up the difference in the attitude and behaviour of women in Bhagwanpur towards banking.

For starters, women's lagging access to banks in Bhagwanpur becomes evident through the account-ownership count of the programme participants who are discussants in the FGDs. Of the 10 discussants in each programme block, all 10 and nine discussants hold bank accounts in the Lalitpur and Aurai respectively, while Bhagwanpur has the least number at only three. Moreover, even among women who hold bank accounts, those in Bhagwanpur are the most inactive. A considerable seven out of 10 women in Lalitpur and all nine women in Aurai say they visited the bank in the last six months, while only a single woman in Bhagwanpur did so. The characteristics of the focus group discussants with regard to banking are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Religious demographics and banking status of focus group discussants in qualitative study sites in three blocks

		Number of discussants		
		Lalitpur	Aurai	Bhagwanpur
Religious demographics	Hindu	10	8	1
	Muslim	None	2	9
	Have bank accounts (personal)	10	9	3
Banking status	Visited bank in last six months	7	9	1
	Visited alone	7	7	None

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

While sampling for the qualitative component of the study, we had ensured that the demographic composition of all three focus groups is largely homogenous in terms of the discussants' age, marital status etc. But our sampling had not considered the discussants' religion. However, interactions on ground unravel the religious identities of Bhagwanpur's discussants to be distinct from those in the two other focus groups. Whereas all 10 discussants in Lalitpur and eight in Aurai are Hindu, the bulk of discussants in Bhagwanpur, at nine, are Muslims. And this religious composition of their focus group is, in fact, representative of their Muslim-majority village, observe Bhagwanpur's focus group discussants. Confirming which, the deputy sarpanch of the panchayat that comprises three villages in the Bhagwanpur block including the one under study, informs that these villages are indeed peopled with 70 per cent Muslims. Of the total Muslim population at 3400, he reports, three-fourths and one-fourth are Deobandis and Barelvis respectively. Deobandis are said to have 'a very puritanical and orthodox

outlook (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 1998). While the Barelvis as described as ‘moderate Sunni Muslims (Alawi & Schwartz, 2010). To add to the complexity of the sect-composition, all the Barelvis and 31 per cent of the Deobandis in the three villages are Rajputs. Rajput Muslims, as per the deputy sarpanch, are ‘upper-caste’, ‘affluent’ and ‘extremely orthodox’.

B. Understanding barriers

The combined conservatism of the Deobandi and Rajput Muslim elders reigns supreme in the study village, shares the deputy sarpanch. Corroborating which, women discussants and key informants — such as community leaders, teachers from neighbourhood schools, members from local NGOs and programme field staff — speak of the curbs imposed on Muslim girls and women in their locality.¹³ These barriers keep women from education, employment, as also finances and banks, and are given to being grouped under two broad categories: i) Socio-religious; ii) Economic

1. Socio-religious barriers to financial inclusion for Muslim women

Daughters are generally not sent to non-Muslim schools, and commuting for higher studies is rarely ever allowed. Madarasas in the neighbourhood, where only the Quran is taught, are the permissible learning centres for girls for most families; that too usually only till the girls attain puberty. Girls and women are expected to stay indoors. Marriage, raising children, caregiving and household chores are taught and learnt to be women’s sole duties. All of these rigid rules hamper the social and economic growth of the communities’ women, including their financial inclusion. The need for women to own separate bank accounts is unrecognised — accounts of male members are seen as family accounts. Banks are perceived as public places, jostling with men and strangers. And unless she is a widow or destitute and dependent on government dole for her family’s survival, observes a rare woman graduate from the community, a woman visiting the bank is considered ‘shameless’.

¹³ The qualitative data cited here are from interviews held with programme participants and key informants from Bhagwanpur who were the study’s subjects in its first part, ‘Discovering barriers’.

The interview guide for this round of data collection is as follows:

‘The adult literacy classes for women ran in three districts, Bhagwanpur, Aurai and Lalitpur. We administered math and Hindi tests in all three places. Women in Bhagwanpur stood first in the Hindi and second in math tests. But when we asked women in all three places whether they have bank accounts, Bhagwanpur’s women came last. They are in fact at the bottom with regard to owning bank accounts, going to banks, and using bank accounts.

Question 1: Why do you think women here are at the bottom with regard to owning bank accounts, going to banks and using bank accounts?

(Prompt question: Your village in Bhagwanpur is Muslim-dominated. Does this have anything to do with fewer women going to banks, and using banks?)

Question 2: What do you think should, and can be, done to encourage women from your area, and community, to use banks?’

Also, if restrictions on mobility saw families disallowing their women and girls from going to schools, markets, banks earlier, these curbs have intensified now. The polarised political environment of the times has added to the insecurities of the Muslims, emphasise the community's male leadership. As the unravelling situation unleashes more fear, Muslim families put firmer stops on their women from partaking in activities that require stepping out. Eighty per cent of the men in the village, shares the deputy sarpanch, insist women stay at home, and that shopping, banking etc. are done by boys and men.

Extracts from discussions and interviews conducted in Bhagwanpur listing the socio-religious barriers imposed on women by their Muslim-majority communities are listed below

Qualitative findings on socio-religious barriers to financial inclusion for Muslim women

RESPONDENT TYPE

Neo-literate Muslim woman programme participant

EXTRACT

- I wanted to go to school, my grandfather didn't allow. My chances of going to school, also getting out of home, shrank as I grew up.
- At the mardrasa we are taught to read and recite the Quran. I can't read Hindi, so can't read anything when I go out. I don't have the confidence to go to a bank, nor do I know what to do there.
- We are illiterate, and in purdah. It is uncomfortable, and difficult, for us to find our way outside. Going to banks is hard. It makes me nervous.
- Our families and communities do not consider it safe for women to get out of homes and neighbourhoods. Visiting banks requires commute.
- The bank account of a male member in the family is treated as the family's account. Families don't see the need for women to have separate accounts.

KEY INFORMANT

Deputy Sarpanch:

- Ours is a conservative Muslim community. Betis, bahu, biwis (daughters, daughters-in-law and wives) are kept indoors. Girls are rarely sent to school. They are disallowed going out to work.
- Ours is a Muslim-dominated village, residents here belong to one of two conservative Islamic sects. Women don't have permission to participate in matters outside their homes. Many families do not allow their women and girls to go to schools, markets, banks.

- The (polarised) political environment has added to the (Muslim) community's insecurities and fears. Men are increasingly scared of the (unravelling) situation, and stop women from partaking in activities that require stepping out. Eighty per cent of men here insist women stay home, and that shopping, banking etc. are done by men.

Graduate Muslim woman, principal of a local private middle-school:

- Families here don't send girls to regular schools as it is likely to spoil their characters. Girls are sent to madrasas, and pulled out when their periods start.
- Banks are public places, crowded with men, accessible to strangers. This means that if a woman is in the bank, the community judges her as being characterless and shameless. Or else, they think, she would be a widow or destitute.
- Women do not have unqualified freedom here. Our community follows its culture, obeying elders is a must, and they are old-fashioned, against modernity. Women without purdah, going out of home for work, even to banks, is considered haram (forbidden or proscribed by Islamic law). Women follow these dictates.

Literacy instructor, a local Muslim woman:

- Girls from the Muslim community here are not permitted to commute and travel. If they move out of home and village, it has to necessarily be with family members or in a group. This stops girls from opening and transacting bank accounts.

Founder, NGO imparting financial literacy trainings in rural North India:

- The few Muslim girls who come to school have their faces covered with mesh (jhali) under burqaas. Any interactions that women have to be involved in are best avoided by Muslim families. Coming to school is in itself an uncomfortable journey for girls, visiting banks to draw scholarship money is impossible. Bank accounts are managed by fathers, husbands and sons.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

2 Economic barriers to financial inclusion for Muslim women

The impoverished Muslim families that comprise the majority population of the study village have no compelling reasons to engage with banks at all, let alone own multiple bank accounts, including for women. Pointing at the lack of employment and business opportunities in the area, especially for Muslims, the deputy sarpanch argues that banking is not an urgent need for families that barely have money to survive.¹⁴

However, women here, whether from poor families or from the area's affluent and orthodox Rajput Muslim sect, are rarely, if ever at all, allowed independent financial lives. Considering that even Muslim men with

¹⁴ According to the Periodic Labour Force Survey data 2017-18, Muslims constitute 11 per cent of the total workers in India. Their share in total employment is 10.2 per cent and 13.9 per cent in rural and urban areas respectively.

schooling are unemployed, reason community members, women who are mostly without formal schooling are unlikely to find livelihood opportunities. Coupled with the stigma attached to women stepping out to fend for their families, the rare Muslim women who work here are usually from families in penury or without male heads and are almost always engaged in petty home-based work. The meagre earnings of few such women, and the majority others who have no income at all, are impervious to the need for banks.

Meanwhile, the minority number of women in the community who own bank accounts hardly ever use them. Because women without any business or employment have no use for banks, says a woman school principal in the study village. She shares that bank usage for women in the community is limited to those who are old or widows or destitute, and in need of government hand-outs.

Extracts from discussions and interviews conducted in Bhagwanpur listing the economic barriers imposed on women by their Muslim-majority communities are listed below

Qualitative findings on economic barriers to financial inclusion for Muslim women

RESPONDENT TYPE

Neo-literate Muslim woman programme participant

EXTRACT

- Families here have so little money that men see no point in having multiple bank accounts in a single household. There is no need for extra bank accounts.
- Other than a friend who lives far away, I do not know any women, in my extended family or neighbourhood, with a bank account. I have one. But as a one-of case. The maulana at the madarsa had opened it for me when I topped Urdu, and he awarded me Rs. 500. This happened 8-10 years ago. I now use this account to deposit the money I get from the embroidery work I do.
- Women here have no work, no money, what will we do with bank accounts?

KEY INFORMANT

Deputy Sarpanch:

- Only in the last decade has at least one bank account per household become a practice. There has been, and continues to be, little or no employment, nor are there business opportunities and activities in this area. So, banking isn't really an urgent need.

- Even Muslim men, with complete schooling, are unemployed. The future is as bleak for most who are graduates. Obviously then, the women in the community have hardly any earning opportunities.

Graduate Muslim woman, principal of a local private middle-school:

- Women in my immediate and extended family, and my locality, do not work. Some women in my family have bank accounts, but have no use for them.
- In our community, young women don't go to work outside, or to banks. Only older women go to banks, and needy, destitute women work, and go to bank to collect government money, also widows go to collect pensions.
- There are no employment or business opportunities for Muslims, so people see no use in getting into banks and banking.

Literacy instructor, a local Muslim woman:

- The pressure to get girls married is huge in our community. Girls are sent to madarasas, money is saved for their weddings and dowries. There is nothing beyond this for girls; they are kept away from jobs, financial activities, banks.
- The rare Muslim working women found in these parts are sure to be from families that are really poor or with no male head. And even they will most likely be engaged in home-based work, like tailoring and embroidery.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

3. In-community recommendations to overcome barriers

Having gained an understanding of the barriers that keep their girls and women from financial inclusion, we seek the Muslim community's recommendations on how best to overcome these. Topmost among the indigenous solutions offered are: Targeted literacy, livelihood and credit solutions for Muslim women.

The demand for mainstream education coupled with lessons in financial literacy for both girls and adult women is uppermost among the community's women. Learning how to open bank accounts, filling-up forms, etc. are the basic necessary steps, they say, on the road to banking-know-how.

But given that Muslim women have little use for banking services in the absence of independent incomes, emphasise both male and female community members, it is imperative that strategies to ensure their engagement with banks include income-generation opportunities for them. Without the facilitation of home or neighbourhood based work by the government and civil society organisations, women find sharing documents,

photos and visiting banks to open accounts a waste of time, shares an instructor recruited by the programme under study.

A local Muslim woman herself, the instructor adds that women in her community are attracted to her literacy classes, and to opening bank accounts, only if they see these as possible enablers to finding work, or running their existing petty home enterprises better.

Thus, providing Muslim women financial incentives to learn, earn and save is offered as a suggestion to encourage them to bank. Such inducements could variously be scholarships, subsidies and credit solutions at affordable cost for farm and non-farm activities, as also to meet household and personal needs. The local leadership from within the community in fact advance some specific proposals:

- The deputy sarpanch is confident that Muslim women will begin using banks if they start earning. He, therefore, advocates that stipends and grants be provided to women from minority communities to enable them to study and learn skills, such that they become job worthy. Also, that soft loans and subsidies be assigned to Muslim-women led enterprises to encourage them. As an example, he suggests, when the government allocates job contracts to SHGs, those with Muslim women majority membership be given priority and easy credit.
- A financial literacy trainer, who engaged with the programme under study as a guest speaker on several occasions, forwards the idea of generating petty cash schemes on the lines of Kisan Credit Card for Muslim women.¹⁵ Women could, for instance, borrow INR 5000 and pay back in five instalments of Rs 1000 each. Financial products such as these, designed to meet their routine unmet financial needs, would attract women into the banking network.
- Till such banking products targeted to service the particular needs of Muslim women are designed, continues the financial literacy trainer, powerful awareness campaigns must introduce them to what is already available. Presently, the bulk of women, and even men, in ‘closed minority communities such as the Muslims’ are ignorant of existing micro-level incentives and loan schemes, such as the MUDRA loan for instance.¹⁶

15 Under the Kisan Credit Card Scheme, credit cards are issued to farmers on the basis of their holdings to provide them adequate and timely credit support from the banking system for agriculture and production needs, investment credit requirement for agriculture and allied activities, and consumption requirement of farmer households. <https://pmkisan.gov.in/>

16 Launched in 2015, Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY) provides loans up to INR 10 lakhs to non-corporate, non-farm small enterprises through banks for growth and development of micro enterprises. The loan offerings are divided into three stages: Shishu, Kishore and Tarun according to amount of money loaned. <https://www.mudra.org.in/>

Muslim women should be informed of subsidies and loans available for petty-home-based-enterprises that they usually engage with, such as raising poultry and goat-rearing.

- Importantly, bankers, particularly those servicing rural and underprivileged populations, need gender sensitisation training that enables them to assess, understand and accommodate the special needs of women, especially women from conservative minority communities.

Extracts from discussions and interviews conducted in Bhagwanpur listing the ways to overcoming barriers to financial inclusion for Muslim women are listed below

EXTRACT

- Like the literacy classes that we went to, there should be classes to teach women like us how to go to banks, open accounts, fill-up forms. And tell us about benefits and facilities in banks. This would make us less nervous about using banks.

KEY INFORMANT

Deputy Sarpanch:

- Muslim women will use banks if they are involved in financial activities, if they earn. Stipends, grants and subsidies to encourage women of minority communities to study and work can make this happen. For example, while the government is allocating job contracts to SHGs, those with Muslim women majority membership can be given priority, easier loans, extra subsidies etc.

Literacy instructor, a local Muslim woman:

- Most women in villages, especially Muslim women, are interested in joining adult literacy classes and opening bank accounts only if these help them find work or do their work better. And it has to be only home-based or neighbourhood-based work. Such local work has to be facilitated for them, by the government, by NGOs. Without this, women find sharing documents and photos and visiting banks to start an account a waste of time.

Founder, NGO imparting financial literacy trainings in rural North India:

- Banking service providers need to be sensitised to accommodate the special needs of women, and especially women from conservative minority communities.
- A schemes that makes petty cash available for women, with a small credit limit, on the lines of the Kisan Credit Card, would go a long way in

attracting rural women into the banking network. For instance, they could borrow Rs 5000 and pay back in five instalments of Rs 1000 each. Products such as these will encourage women to start banking. Once some women start more will follow.

- Awareness campaigns for women in closed minority communities that introduce them to MUDRA loans should be run aggressively. Women in these communities should be told of micro level incentives and loans available for petty-home-based-enterprises that they mostly engage with, such as raising poultry and goat-rearing.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) of 2015-16

The way forward

The study this article draws from provides robust evidence that the Muslim community realises that a multitude of hurdles confronts its women on their way to financial inclusion. Also, it understands that these barriers stem from restrictions on women imposed by socio-religious practices, including curbing their access to basic literacy and education. Which, in turn, deprive women of independent incomes and economic lives as girls and adults. These in-community realisations are in fact in consonance with external findings from surveys conducted at the national scale; which have Muslim women scoring lower than other Indian women on possessing and deciding how to use money, owning and using bank accounts, as also on awareness and use of microcredit programmes (International Institute for Population Sciences & Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2017).

Most relevantly, the study solicits indigenous recommendations on how the barriers that keep Muslim women away from banks might best be overcome. The suggestions so procured and enlisted in this article indicate that the community is actively thinking of the solutions that must make for milestones on Muslim women's road to financial inclusion. It is encouraging that literacy and livelihood are seen as the most prominent signposts that Muslim women need to get past on their way to the bank.

References

- Alawi, I. A., & Schwartz, S. (2010). Moderate Muslim Leaders Take a Stand: Anti-radical Muslim resistance spreading to India, Pakistan. Center for Islamic Pluralism. <https://www.islamicpluralism.org/1441/moderate-muslim-leaders-take-a-stand>
- Chambers, R. (2008) 'PRA, PLA and Pluralism: Practice and Theory', in The Sage Handbook of Action Research: Participative Inquiry and Practice. Reason, P. and H. Bradbury (eds). Sage.

- Creswell, J. W. (2013). Steps in conducting a scholarly mixed methods study.
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., Ansar, S., & Hess, J. (2018). The Global FinDex Database 2017: Measuring Financial Inclusion and the Fintech Revolution. In Washington, DC: World Bank eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-1259-0>
- Department of Financial Services, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (2021). PMDJY Progress Report. Government of India (GoI). <https://pmjdy.gov.in/account>
- Encyclopaedia Britannica. (1998, July 20). Deoband school | Founder, Beliefs, & History. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Deoband-school>
- International Institute for Population Sciences & Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. (2017). National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4). International Institute for Population Sciences. <https://rchiips.org/nfhs/NFHS-4Reports/India.pdf>
- Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner. Ministry of Home Affairs. (2011). Census of 2011. GoI
- Patel, A., Divakar, P., Prabhakar, R. (2020). 40% Of Jan Dhan Account Holders Could Not Access Govt's COVID-19 Relief: Survey. Indiaspend. <https://www.indiaspend.com/40-of-jan-dhan-account-holders-could-not-access-govts-covid-19-relief-survey/>
- Teddlie, C., & Yu, F. (2007). Mixed methods sampling: A typology with examples. *Journal of mixed methods research*, 1(1), 77-100

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